

ISic1667

A fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

block

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

lost

Last Change

2020-12-04 - Jonathan Prag created the file from current template

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Observed by Orsi 1888-09-09, 'presso il pozzo dell'Ingegnere', Piazza d'Armi, the site of the Roman forum

Coordinates

37.066339, 15.284319

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

A large irregular block of marble, damaged on all sides

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters, damaged at both ends; whether more missing from above and below is unknown

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The L in line two appears tall and narrow with a downward sloping second stroke, more typical of later Roman texts

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]YC(vac.undefin)[---]

2. [---]CLXXV[---]

Apparatus

Text based upon Orsi's drawing in Taccuino 1 p.38

Translation

Commentary

The inscription is the first one to be recorded by Paolo Orsi for Sicily, not more

than 2 days after his arrival on the island in September 1888, and the drawing constitutes the first entry for Sicily in the 'Taccuini' (Orsi's working notebooks). The fragment was recorded in situ and does not seem to have been recovered. Lanteri 2020 discusses and locates the provenance 'pozzo dell'Ingegnere' referenced by Orsi, in the area of Piazza d'Armi.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 371
Orsi, Paolo 2018. I Taccuini. I. Riproduzione anastatica e trascrizione dei
Taccuini 1-4. *Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Monumenti Antichi. Serie Miscellanea*.
Rome. At Tacc. 1, p.38

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